

PROTOTYPING OF AN ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD IDENTIFICATION AND MEASUREMENT DEVICE

Gabriel Henrique Castilho Oliveira, João Victor Alves Ferreira, Matheus Cardoso Medeiros, Dr. Alexandre Maniçoba de Oliveira.

Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of São Paulo, Cubatão Campus.
 castilho.gabriel@aluno.ifsp.edu.br , victor.alves1@aluno.ifsp.edu.br , cardoso.medeiros@aluno.ifsp.edu.br and
 amanicoba@ifsp.edu.br .

Abstract - This article presents the theoretical basis and prototyping for the development of a device capable of identifying electromagnetic waves through barriers and measuring their intensity. The proposed device uses principles of electromagnetic resonance, signal analysis and intensity measurement. In addition, a Matlab simulation of this measurement is presented.

Keywords: Electromagnetic Waves; Intensity; Detection; Electromagnetic Spectrum; Telecommunications

INTRODUCTION

Electromagnetic waves play a central role in modern technology and are used in a variety of areas. The increasing use of devices that emit or receive electromagnetic waves increases the need to monitor and measure the intensity of these waves to ensure the quality of services and avoid unwanted interference [1].

Therefore, the development of devices capable of detecting and measuring electromagnetic waves in different frequency ranges and situations creates enormous potential to be an essential and indispensable technology in the present and in the near future.

BASIC THEORETICAL BASIS

Electromagnetic waves are oscillations of electric and magnetic fields that propagate through space, carrying energy. They are described by Maxwell's equations that exist in both differential and integral form [3], changing for each type of situation encountered. Thus, they form the electromagnetic theory, providing an understanding of the propagation of these waves in different media.

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} &= \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0 \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H} &= \mathbf{J} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t}\end{aligned}$$

Maxwell's equations in differential form

The electromagnetic spectrum is in turn divided into several frequency bands, such as

radio waves, microwaves, infrared, visible light, ultraviolet, X-rays and gamma rays. Each band has specific applications, such as telecommunications, X-rays for bodily injuries, cancer treatment, product quality control, and infrared detection [3].

The intensity of an electromagnetic wave, in turn, is the amount of energy transported per unit area and depends directly on the amplitude of the electric field. Electromagnetic resonance occurs when an instrument, such as an antenna or receiving device, is adjusted to resonate at a specific frequency, as desired, increasing the efficiency in capturing the wave. For the development of an electromagnetic wave detection device, resonance allows the system to identify waves in predefined frequency ranges. After capturing the waves, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is used, as an auxiliary mathematical method, to decompose the signal into its frequency components.

To measure electromagnetic waves in electrical conduits, a powerful sensor with high sensitivity to electric and magnetic fields is required, since measurements would be made through walls and pipes, which would be an obstacle. A more sensitive sensor would provide better quality in filtering field lines and also reduce the error that walls, metal pipes and any other obstacles cause to the device. In addition, sockets and high-voltage generators cause noise and problems with the measurement.

This method allows the device to identify which frequencies are present in the signal, facilitating the detection and analysis of the intensity of the waves. Noise filtering, through digital signal processing (DSP) algorithms, ensures that only the relevant signals are considered.

For the practical part, Maxwell's equation from the Faraday-Lenz Law was used, because thanks to it and the magnetic induction field over time, it is possible to confirm the existence of an electric rotational field in the opposite direction to the field lines [3].

To measure magnetic fields, a hall effect sensor was used. A Hall sensor operates based on the Hall effect, which occurs when a magnetic field is applied perpendicular to a current flowing through a conductor. The magnetic field deflects the charge carriers (electrons or holes), creating a voltage difference across the conductor—this is the Hall voltage. In a Hall sensor, this voltage is measured and used to determine the strength and direction of the magnetic field. Hall sensors are commonly used for detecting magnetic fields, measuring magnetic flux density, and for proximity or positioning sensing in various applications.

Fig. 1 - How a hall sensor works [5].

MATLAB SIMULATION

The simulation developed in Matlab aimed to simulate the capture of signals at different frequencies and measure their intensity. The code implements the generation of two sinusoidal waves with different frequencies and applies the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to convert the signal from the time domain to the frequency domain, allowing the identification of the frequency components present [4], [2].

The code has a solid theoretical foundation in Maxwell's Equations, which describe the interaction between electric and magnetic fields in space. The relationship between the variation of the magnetic field, generating an electric field, is described by Faraday's Law, and is implemented in the code through the generation of sinusoidal waves that simulate the propagation of electromagnetic fields.

The code simulates the generation of electromagnetic waves by combining two sinusoidal waves, which represents time-varying fields. This relates to the *Ampère-Maxwell Law*, which describes how magnetic fields are generated from changes in electric fields.

A frequency analysis is performed using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to decompose the time-domain signal into its frequency components, allowing for the detection of specific frequencies and their intensities. This is linked to *Gauss's Law for the electric field*, as the magnitude from the FFT reflects the field intensity and the energy carried by the wave.

Noise filtering removes low-amplitude components, improving accuracy by isolating relevant frequencies for a cleaner spectrum analysis.

Fig. 2 - Graph of the Captured Electromagnetic Signal

Fig. 3 - Frequency Spectrum Graph

The simulation results showed effective capture of complex signals, resulting in a total signal composed of two sine waves of 50 Hz and 150 Hz. The total signal intensity, calculated from the sum of the magnitudes, reflected the amount of energy transported, being essential for signal evaluation. In addition, the filtering applied to the spectrum eliminated noise, resulting in a graph that displays only the relevant frequencies. In short, the simulation demonstrated that the device can be efficient in

capturing, analyzing and measuring electromagnetic waves.

With that established, we started prototyping the device using the parts: Arduino Nano, 128x64 OLED Display, 1x UGN3503 Hall Effect Sensor and a 9V battery.

- **BASED ON THE SCHEME:**

An electronic diagram was made using the Arduino Nano on the protoboard as a more symbolic representation of the device. The electronic circuit was also made using three transistors, connected in Darlington to amplify the signal detected by the coil and a directly polarized diode, which, when not receiving electric current, thus closes the circuit, showing that there are no fields detected.

Fig. 4 - Magnetic Field Meter

Fig. 5 - Alternating Voltage Detector

$$\oint \vec{E} \cdot d\vec{l} = - \frac{d\phi_B}{dt}$$

Maxwell's Equation in Integral Form of the Faraday-Lenz Law

This Maxwell equation helps to set up the voltage detector. It was created through the Faraday-Lenz Law, which tells us that the closed

integral over a length (a current-carrying wire) is equal to the difference in the derivative of the magnetic flux of the magnetic induction field over time. Where this length is infinitesimal.

Because with this equation, we can calculate, using the flux and magnetic induction field, the existence of wiring, conduits and electrical cables. In addition to measuring the intensity of the voltage and current that pass through.

RESULTS

Tests carried out on the prototype ended up showing promising results, with the device proving capable of capturing electromagnetic signals. However, the prototype still has significant limitations in terms of range, which restricts its applicability in scenarios where the distance between the emission source and the device is greater.

CONCLUSION

However, for the device to reach a functional level suitable for use in large and complex environments, it will need to be optimized in its range and sensitivity to more distant sources. In short, the prototype has proven effective in the initial stages, and is an important first step towards implementation and improvement, but technical improvements are essential.

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